

DEVELOPING RUBRICS FOR ASSESSING LINGUISTIC COMPETENCE IN HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS

Karimova Mohinur

Uzbekistan State World Languages University
Faculty of English Philology

***Abstract.** The purpose of this paper is to provide an overview of “rubric” in language testing and assessment and to highlight the parts of a rubric through various dimensions. It sets forth objectives and types of the rubric used. As the paper will illustrate, language testing and assessment in SLA demands many facets to take the learners to the “successful learner point”. Being aware of the effective use of rubrics reflects the robustness of this critical assessment process.*

***Keywords.** Rubric, assessment, dimensions of a rubric, measurement.*

Introduction. The word “rubric” comes from the Latin word for “red.” It was once used to signify the highlights of a legal decision as well as the directions for conducting religious services, found in the margins of liturgical books—both written in red. In a broad sense, rubric refers to a term which has existed in English for more than 600 years and during that time, mostly it has meant a set of “printed rules or instructions”. However, in educational sense, it refers to different categories such as criteria for assessment, evaluation of learning, gradients of learning of a set of instructions etc.

Main part

A good activity never guarantees the accurate determination of a student’s competency at a given task. At this point, rubrics stand for this main requirement. Since it specifies the skill being examined and what constitutes various levels of performance success. In order to construct a good rubric focus on “what to measure exactly, how to measure performance and decision on what a passing level of performance competency is” plays the key role. Even though based on the

general guidelines a general rubric design may be organized and be used multiple times.

Here is the process in detail:

1. **Defining the Behavior to Be Assessed** Expected student outcomes, what they should accomplish at the end of each unit and end of each term should be clarified. For this, some questions should be asked: - What concept, skill or knowledge am I trying to assess? - What should my students know? - At what level should my students be performing? - What type of knowledge is being assessed: reasoning, memory or process?

2. **Choosing the Activity** After the determination of the purpose of the assessment, you should decide on an activity and consider issues regarding time constraints, resources, and how much data is required.

3. **Defining the Criteria** The Third step after the decision on activity and tasks to be used, is the definition of which elements of the project/task will be used to find the success of the students' performance.

There are two dominant types of rubrics: holistic and analytic rubrics. However, primary trait and multiple trait rubrics are also commonly used. In comparison with each other, it is hard to tell which types or types are better to use since it depends on the task, and key criteria to be fulfilled by the learners.

Rubrics are essential tools for all language teachers in this age of communicative and task-based teaching and assessment—tools that allow us to efficiently communicate to our students what we are looking for in the productive language abilities of speaking and writing and then effectively assess those.

Conclusion. Proficiency scales and rubrics are vital components of a strong Local Comprehensive Assessment System (LCAS). They provide a clear vision for teaching and learning that enables all stakeholders to know where students are in to identified expectations. Additionally, proficiency scales and rubrics help build a common understanding for determining proficiency and reducing teacher bias. Alternatively, when criteria are vague, implicit stereotypes can “fill in the blanks”

and create an inequitable assessment of student work (Quinn, 2020). Finally, clear expectations for assessing learning allow students to demonstrate their knowledge and growth over time in multiple ways and therefore can support flexible pathways to graduation.

REFERENCES

1. McTighe J. Doughty K. and Carbaugh E. M. (2020). Designing authentic performance tasks and projects: tools for meaningful learning and assessment. ASCD. Quinn, D. M. (2020).
2. Experimental Evidence on Teachers' Racial Bias in Student Evaluation: The Role of Grading Scales. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 42, 375-392.
3. American Council on the Teaching of Foreign Languages. (1999). ACTFL performance guidelines for K-12 learners. Yonkers, NY: ACTFL.
4. Wolf, K., Connelly, M., & Komara, A. (2008). A Tale of Two Rubrics: Improving Teaching and Learning Across the Content Areas through Assessment.